

ENHANCED SECURITY FRAMEWORK FOR CLOUD- LINKED IoT

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ABSTRACT

Internet of Things (IoT) is evaluated there are over a billion web clients and quickly expanding. In any case, there are a larger number of things on the web than there are individuals on the web. This is the thing that it has been for the most part mean, when it has been say internet of things. There are a great many gadgets with sensors that are connected up together utilizing networks that create an ocean of information. The issue is all information needs to remain secured, unaltered, and held on at each phase of an IoT solution. This incorporates database servers, distributed components, back-end analytics and communication infrastructure, crosswise over conceivably adverse environments and remote locations.

Regardless, it is defenseless against eavesdropping which speaks to a hazard to protection and security of the customer. The security of information movement winds up evidently imperative since the interchanges over open network happen habitually. It is thusly fundamental that the information movement over the framework is scrambled. To give the QoS, the Cloud-connected IoT security is the basic piece of the specialist organizations. This paper is focusing on issue relating to the Cloud-connected IoT security in virtual condition.. It has been propose a method COOPERATION KEY PROCESSING for giving information process and security in Cloud-connected IoT utilizing Elliptical Curve Cryptography ECC and Hash Map. Support, delineates the security services consolidates era of key, encryption and decryption in virtual condition.

Key Words: *IoT, Cloud, SaaS, ECC, QoS, Encryption, Decryption, Hash Map.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Internet of Things (IoT) [1] is a multidisciplinary area that covers an extensive number of subjects from absolutely specialized issues (e.g., semantic queries, routing protocols), to a blend of specialized and societal issues (usability, security, privacy), and also social and business topics. IoT applications, both existing and potential, are similarly different. On the off chance that it has been are to abridge every one of them into one, it is empowering the machine impression of this present reality and consistent collaborations with it. Environmental and personal health observing, checking and control of mechanical procedures including farming, savvy spaces, and brilliant urban communities are quite recently a portion of the cases of IoT applications.

Internet of Things systems may help bolster the communication amongst "things" and consider more mind boggling structures like Distributed Computing [2] and the advancement of Distributed applications. Right now, Internet of

Things structures appear to concentrate on constant information logging arrangements offering some premise to work with numerous "things" and have them interface. Future advancements may prompt particular Software improvement conditions to make the product to work with the equipment utilized as a part of the Internet of Things.

A platform is anything that can run applications and store information. In an organization's data center, for instance, you may have PCs running Windows Server and other programming that give a platform to your in-house applications. A cloud platform is a similar thing: It's an establishment for running applications and storing information. The greatest contrast is that it keeps running in server farms possessed by an outer specialist organization, for example, Microsoft, Amazon, Google, IBM, Rack Space and so forth., and it's gotten to by means of the Internet. Another distinction is as opposed to depend on precisely the same that your current in-house platform utilizes, cloud platforms regularly utilize something somewhat unique. For instance, Microsoft's cloud stage runs Windows Azure as opposed to Windows Server

2. CLOUD PLATFORM

Cloud Platform is a cloud computing service by Cloud Service Providers (CSP) [3] that offers hosting on the same supporting infrastructure that CSP uses internally for end-user products like Cloud based Search engine. Cloud Platform provides developer products to build a range of programs from simple websites to complex applications.

2.1 Benefits of using the cloud platform [4]

- Faster deployment of new business capabilities
- Lower-risk business innovation
- Global scale and global reach
- More intelligent IT spending

2.2 The risk factors of using the cloud platform

- Outsourcing to an external provider
- Storing data outside your organization (This is clearly a risk but how much risk is appropriate or acceptable is a business decision.)
- Vendor lock-in (so far there is no easy way to port an application developed for one cloud provider to another cloud provider.)
- Major risks is Security (Cloud- linked IoT Security)

3. RELLIPTIC CURVES CRYPTOGRAPHY

In ECC, using mathematical curves to encrypt and decrypt data by an asymmetric cryptography algorithm which contains some high level calculation. It is similar to RSA as it's asymmetric but it uses a very small length key as

compared to RSA. ECC is an asymmetric cryptography algorithm which involves the following steps:

3.1 ECC Encryption

- 1) A curve is defined by using mathematical equation
- 2) For both the receiver and sender, using that curve, the public key is generated.
- 3) From the key pair pool, a shared secret key is generated
- 4) An encryption key is generated by means of the shared secret key.
- 5) The data is encrypted by using the symmetric encryption algorithm and encryption key.

3.2 ECC Decryption

The sender will either share the curve with receiver or sender and receiver will have the same use for the same curve type. Also, sender will share its public key with receiver.

- 1) Generate public private Key pair using the same curve for that curve for receiver.
- 2) Regenerate a shared secret key using private key of receiver and public key of sender.
- 3) From that shared secret key, generate an encryption key
- 4) Using that encryption key and symmetric encryption algorithm, decrypt the data. phrases.

For papers published in translated journals, first give the English citation, then the original foreign-language citation [6].

Table1. Comparison of Major Public Key Encryption Algorithm

ECC	ELGAMAL (DIFFIE-HELLMAN)	RSA	
Not patented, but many low level optimizations are	Expired in 1997	Expired in 2001	Patent status
Discrete logarithm of elliptic curve	Discrete logarithm over a finite field	Integer factorization	Mathematical problem
Exponential	Exponential	Sub exponential	Best known attack
160 bits	1024 bits	1024 bits	Average key size
Certicom	None	RSA Security	Corporate "champion"

4. CLOUD- LINKED IOT ATTACKS

Internet of things (IoT) technologies are getting ready to transform the way it has been work and live; if one thing can prevent the IoT from transforming the way it has been live and work, it will be a breakdown in security. The goal of the paper is to integrate and evaluate the standardized technique COOPERATION KEY PROCESSING Cloud- linked IoT using Elliptical Curve Cryptography (ECC) in modern Internet of Things architectures consisting of things (sensor nodes), clouds, smartphones, and end-users.

4.1 Physical Attacks

These types of attacks tamper with the hardware components and are relatively harder to perform because it requires expensive material. Some examples are de-packaging of chip, layout reconstruction, micro-probing, and particle beam techniques [6].

4.2 Side Channel attacks

These attacks are based on “side channel Information” that can be retrieved from the encryption device that is neither the plaintext to be encrypted nor the cipher text resulting from the encryption process. Encryption devices produce timing information that is easily measurable, radiation of various sorts, power consumption statistics, and more. Side channel attacks makes use of some or all of this information to recover the key the device is using. It is based on the fact that logic operations have physical characteristics that depend on the input data. Examples of side channel information are timing attacks, power analysis attacks, fault analysis attacks, electromagnetic attacks, and environmental attacks [7].

4.3 Cryptanalysis attacks

These attacks are focused on the cipher text and they try to break the encryption, i.e. find the encryption key to obtain the plaintext. Examples of cryptanalysis attacks include Cipher text-only attack, Known-plaintext attack, Chosen-plaintext attack, Man-in-the-middle attack, etc [8].

4.4. Software Attacks

Software Attacks are the major source of security vulnerabilities in any system. Software attacks exploit implementation vulnerabilities in the system through its own communication interface. This kind of attack includes exploiting buffer overflows and using Trojan horse programs, worms or viruses to deliberately inject malicious code into the system [9].

4.5. Network Attacks

Wireless communications systems are vulnerable to network security attacks due to the broadcast nature of the transmission medium. Basically attacks are classified as active and passive attacks. Examples of Passive attacks include Monitor and Eavesdropping, Traffic Analysis, Camouflage Adversaries, etc. Examples of Active attacks

include Denial of Service Attacks, Node Subversion, Node Malfunction, Node Capture, Node Outage, Message Corruption, False Node, Routing Attacks, etc [10].

4.6. Major Security concerns for IOT

- a) Secure network access: This provides a network connection or service access only if the device is authorized.
- b) Secure data communication: It includes authenticating communicating peers, ensuring confidentiality and integrity of communicated data, preventing repudiation of a communication transaction, and protecting the identity of communicating entities.

Figure1: Cloud- linked IoT Attacks

5. ENHANCED SECURITY FRAMEWORK FOR CLOUD- LINKED IoT

Figure2: Encryption phase

Figure3: Decryption phase

5.1 Encryption and Decryption -Give-And-Take Key Processing Algorithm

The Elliptic Curve encryption with Hash Map (ECCH) algorithm does have a fairly complicated set of domain parameters that describe what curve is being used. However, after the parameters are chosen (either generated or selected from a table), the actual algorithm for encryption is very simple. The domain conditions are as follows:

5.1.1 PARAMETERS

1. The field, either p , a large prime or $2m$. These values can be predetermined and preselected and may be reused. The size of p or m needs to be sufficiently large in order to allow Condition 3.
2. Curve coefficients a, b that are elements of the field that define an elliptic curve E .
3. A prime number r that divides the number of points on E .
4. A curve point G of order r . The size of r (in bits) is what determines the strength of the EC family; normally the minimum is 161 bits.
5. If a binary field is used, a parameter specifying the coordinate representation.
6. Optionally, a cofactor k such that $k = o(E)/r$.
7. Additionally, in some cases, $GCD(k, r) = 1$.

The generation for prime fields isn't so bad, but the binary case requires using various tables to aid in computation. Fortunately, the domain parameters can be reused. If that sounds odd, think of being able to "reuse" integers even though you generated an RSA key pair. However, unlike RSA key pairs, these parameters will need validation.

Using our previous example,

it has been use the $E(\text{field} = F_{11}, a = 1, b = 1, o(E) = 14)$. The point $G = (6, 5)$ has order 7, since $7 \times (6, 5) = O$. And, finally, $k = 14/7 = 2$, and $GCD(7, 2) = 1$.

5.1.2 KEY GENERATION

Once you have the all the domain parameters (either generated or validated), generating keys is very simple:

1. Pick a random integer $0 < s < r$.
2. Compute a point on the curve $W = sG$.

W is the public key, and s is the private key.

Key generation is fast once the domain parameters are computed. There are other algorithms for validating public keys to make sure points aren't completely bogus. Using our example again, we'll pick $s = 4$, so $W = 4G = 4(6, 5) = (3, 3)$.

5.1.3 KEY AGREEMENTS AND ENCRYPTION

Just as in the Diffie-Hellman case, it has been can define key agreements. Regardless of the representation or field, the process is identical. Given two sets of key pairs $(W1, s1)$ and $(W2, s2)$, the shared secret value is computed by using:

$$s2W1 = s1W2$$

The shared secret is a point on the curve, and the coordinates are effectively random. However it's traditional to use just the x-coordinate. The bits that make up the x-coordinate can be used as a secret key for a symmetric cipher. Continuing our example using a key of $((3, 3), 4)$; we'll pick another key $((0, 10), 5)$ and compute the secret.

$$5(3, 3) = (6, 6)$$

$$4(0, 10) = (6, 6)$$

5.1.4 HASH FUNCTION

K = key

M = message

H = cryptographic hash function

$$\text{HMAC} = H(k \parallel m)$$

A more secure approach is the so-called padded envelope, where you make sure the internal hash algorithm is iterated more than once by adding padding after the first key:

$$\text{HMAC} = H(k \parallel p \parallel m \parallel k)$$

Now that it has been have a secret value, encryption and decryption work identically to the regular discrete logarithm version.

6. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

6.1 MAPPING THE DEPENDENCIES BETWEEN THE PARAMETER SETTING AND THE EFFICIENCY FEATURES

Tests were made with Proposed Process, ECC and with RSA during the

- Key Generation
- Establishment Common Parameters
- Encryption
- Decryption
- Signing
- Signature Verification

6.1.1 THE MEASURED DATA WERE

- The time of execution
- and the size of data, namely:
 - Size of the Common Parameter Files,
 - Size of the Public and Secret Key Files,
 - Size of the Encrypted Data Files,
 - Size of the Signature Files

6.1.2 THE PARAMETERS OF THE OPERATIONS ARE:

- the size of the applied key
- the size and content of the input data

Our experiments used the Apache 2.0.45 web server compiled with OpenSSL-SNAP-20030309 using the Sun Forte Developer 7 C compiler without architecture-specific optimizations. This snapshot of the development version of OpenSSL includes ECC code contributed by Sun Microsystems Laboratories [29]. Enhancements were made to the mod ssl component of Apache in order to make it ECC aware. It has been ran the server on a single 900 MHz UltraSPARC III processor with 2GB of memory inside a Sun Fire V480 server running the Ubuntu 16.4 operating system.⁵ For the HTTPS clients, it has been used a prototype Sun Fire server equipped with seven 900 MHz UltraSPARC III processors, 14GB of memory and also running the Solaris 9 operating system. The server and client

machines were connected via a 100Mb Ethernet network.

6.2 ANALYSIS OF EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS - COMPARISON OF ECC AND RSA MICRO BENCHMARKS

Table 2 shows a comparison of the RSA and ECCH cryptographic operations performed by an Cloud-IoT server. It has been used the OpenSSL speed program to measure RSA decryption and ECDH operation for different key sizes (a minor enhancement was made for collecting RSA-1536 numbers). These micro-benchmarks highlight ECCH’s performance advantage over RSA for different security levels. Note how ECCH’s performance advantage increases even faster than its key-size advantage as security needs increase.

Table2. Measured performance of public-key algorithms

RSA-2048	ECCH-224	RSA-1536	ECCH-192	RSA-1024	ECCH-160	
17.8	195.5	36.4	268.5	114.3	271.3	Ops/sec
21.4 : 1		7.4 : 1		271.3		Performance ratio
01:09.1		1:08		2.4 : 1		Key-size ratio

6.3. RELATIVE COSTS IN AN HTTPS FETCH

Figure 4 shows the average time taken by the server to fulfill an HTTPS request for different page sizes and public keys with no session reuse. It has been used micro benchmark results for ECCH, RSA, RC4, and SHA to estimate the relative costs involved. RSA decryption continues to be the dominant cost in all of these cases. According to SPECWeb99 which models real-world web traffic, 85% of the files are under 10KB. For such files, RSA takes up anywhere between 63% to 88% of the overall time depending on the security level. This suggests that efforts to reduce the RSA cost or replace it with a cheaper alternative will have a significant payoff. Indeed, it has been see that using ECCH reduces overall processing time at the server by 29% to 86% across the entire range of page sizes in our study.

Figure4: Relative costs in an data transaction

7. CONCLUSION

The above analysis suggests that the use of ECCH cipher suites offers significant performance benefits to IoT clients and servers especially as security needs increase. Already, there is considerable momentum behind widespread adoption of the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and RSA which specifies the use of 128-bit, 192-bit and 256-bit symmetric keys. As indicated in Table 2, key sizes for public-key cryptosystems used to establish AES and RSA keys will correspondingly need to increase from current levels. Furthermore, as users become increasingly sensitive to on-line privacy issues, they are likely to demand IoT protection for more of their transactions. It has been believe these trends bode well for broader deployment of ECCH, in not just wireless environments but also traditional servers/cloud server environments. Besides Cloud-IoT, It has been also added ECCH support. It has been now targeting ECCH support in these servers and intends to perform a similar study for their representative workloads.

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